

ConcrEITS: an electrical impedance interrogator for concrete damage detection using self-sensing repairs

Jack McAlorum ^{1,*} , Marcus Perry ¹, Christos Vlachakis ¹ and Andrew Ward ¹

¹ Civil and Environmental Engineering Department, University of Strathclyde; jack.mcalorum@strath.ac.uk

* Correspondence: jack.mcalorum@strath.ac.uk

Abstract: Concrete infrastructure requires continuous monitoring to ensure any new damage or repair failures are detected promptly. A cost-effective combination of monitoring and maintenance would be highly beneficial in the rehabilitation of existing infrastructure. Alkali-activated materials have been used as concrete repairs and as sensing elements for temperature, moisture and chlorides. However, damage detection using self-sensing repairs has yet to be demonstrated, and commercial interrogation solutions are expensive. Here we present the design of a low-cost tomographic impedance interrogator, denoted the “ConcrEITS”, capable of crack detection and location in concrete using conductive repair patches. Results show that for pure material blocks ConcrEITS is capable of measuring 4-probe impedance with a root mean square error of $\pm 5.4\%$ when compared to a commercially available device. For tomographic measurements, ConcrEITS is able to detect and locate cracks in patches adhered to small concrete beam samples undergoing 4-point bending. In all 6 samples tested, crack locations were clearly identified by the contour images gained from tomographic reconstruction. Overall, this system shows promise as a cost-effective combined solution for monitoring and maintenance of concrete infrastructure. We believe further up-scaled testing should follow this research before implementing the technology in a field trial.

Keywords: Damage, concrete, repair, sensor, Alkali-activated material, low-cost tomographic impedance interrogator, crack detection and location

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1. Introduction

Concrete degradation is an ever-growing global challenge as more structures reach the end of their design life [1]. Asset managers must detect, locate, and quantify this damage, ideally both before and after remediation. Continuous non-destructive monitoring systems for inferring and locating damage include accelerometers [2], fibre-optic sensors [3], wave propagation [4], and robotic imaging [5]. A key limitation of these techniques is that they cannot perform direct damage measurements that are both continuous in time and space (i.e. fully distributed). Other deterioration measures include field inspections to predict corrosion caused by carbonation and chloride [6]. These methods are usually destructive in nature, requiring coring of the structure [7]. Direct electrical impedance tomography and spectroscopy (EITS) measurements of the concrete itself, or of self-sensing coatings is compatible with continuous and distributed monitoring and can be non-destructive. There is precedent for EIT’s use in structural health monitoring more generally (beyond concrete), and an excellent review is provided in [8]. In short, EIT provides the ability to reconstruct a contour image of a cell’s conductivity distribution in 2-D or 3-D. This can be exploited to provide a distributed measurement of any variable that affects conductivity. The image reconstruction algorithm is key in realising high spatial resolution EIT images [9]. Algorithms vary by application, with open source software available for testing on real data. [10].

38 The major challenge facing concrete monitoring applications is that existing EITS
39 interrogators tend to be expensive (\$15k USD), plug-in bench systems which are optimised
40 for chemical analyses and medical imaging. There is a clear need for low-power, low-
41 cost and portable EITS interrogators optimised for wireless concrete structural health
42 monitoring if this technology is to gain wider industry application. Low-power, portable
43 devices for corrosion and electrochemical testing of concrete has been demonstrated and
44 examples have been summarised by Segura et al. [11], including a wireless potentiostat
45 [12]. Electrical *resistance* tomography (ERT) has been demonstrated for crack detection
46 in concrete via an electrically conductive paint (although the interrogators used were
47 not outlined) [13]. No examples of a low-cost, low-power, portable EITS interrogator
48 for crack detection and location in concrete could be found in literature at the time of
49 writing.

50 Recent work by the present authors has outlined the use of alkali-activated material
51 (AAM) as a self-sensing non-structural concrete repair. We have demonstrated that
52 changes in concrete and AAM repair material moisture [14], temperature [15] and strain
53 [16] are encoded as a measurable shift in the bulk electrical impedance of discrete samples
54 (i.e. no tomographic imaging was demonstrated).

55 In this paper, we present ‘ConcrEITS’: a new low-cost EITS interrogator which can
56 provided continuous and distributed measurements of concrete specimens via electrically
57 conductive coatings, such as AAM repairs. The system is capable of both single 4-probe
58 impedance and 16-probe tomographic impedance measurements of AAM patches at
59 various AC driving frequencies. Here, we benchmark ConcrEITS against a commercial
60 4-probe impedance analyser before validating it’s ability to detect and locate temperature
61 changes and concrete cracking in small lab-scale specimens. ConcrEITS is in the proof-
62 of-concept stage, and results are demonstrated at small scale. Future work will look to
63 demonstrate ConcrEITS at full scale.

64 2. Materials and Methods

65 2.1. Self-sensing repair coatings for concrete

66 2.1.1. Brief theory

67 Alkali-activated materials (AAMs) are a class of curable cementitious materials
68 produced by mixing an alkaline activator solution (such as sodium hydroxide and sodium
69 silicate) with a precursor rich in silicon and aluminium (such as metakaolin). For more
70 information on the fabrication of AAMs, their deployment and curing methods, and their
71 use as repairs, see [17] and [18]. Initially, AAMs are workable enough to pour but cure
72 into a high strength brittle material, as shown in Fig. 1a.

73 After curing, AAMs act as electrolytic conductors due to the presence of mobile
74 sodium ions in their matrix [14]. Their inert electrical impedance, $Z(\omega, t)$, can be found
75 by measuring the material’s voltage response, $V_m(\omega, t)$ under an alternating current
76 excitation $I_a(\omega, t)$ as:

$$Z(\omega, t) = \frac{V_m(\omega, t)}{I_a(\omega, t)} \quad (1)$$

77 where ω is the frequency term of the applied alternating current. The AAM’s impedance,
78 $Z(t)$, will vary due to measurands including temperature, humidity, strain and sodium
79 chloride [18]. Alternating current (AC), rather than direct current (DC), is used to
80 prevent migration of the sodium ions through the matrix.

81 2.1.2. Mix design

82 The large number of variables involved in AAM mixing can cause contradicting
83 conclusions from similar studies. Simple factors such as mixing technique and duration
84 or even location of sourced aluminosilicate can change the mechanical properties of the
85 final product [19,20]. It is likely that the “optimal” mechanical performing mix design
86 will be unsuitable for certain applications. For these reasons, generally a trial and error

87 approach to mix design (with reference to previous reports) for a particular application
88 is required.

89 In this work, the focus is on acquiring a pourable and strong surface coating that
90 can adhere well to a concrete specimen until cracking, with sufficient conductivity for
91 sensing. The three main factors in a mix design include:

- 92 • Solid:liquid ratio
- 93 • Na_2SiO_3 :NaOH ratio
- 94 • Additives

95 Metakaolin was chosen over other aluminosilicates (fly-ash, Blast furnace slag (BFS)) for
96 4 reasons:

- 97 1. Requires a higher liquid content which increases conductivity [21].
- 98 2. Has more consistent particle sizes than fly-ash [22].
- 99 3. Is a natural resource compared to fly-ash (by-product of coal combustion) and BFS
100 (by-product of iron/steel smelting).
- 101 4. More suitable as a repair than BFS [23].

102 However, Zhang et al. [24] suggest replacing a small quantity of metakaolin with fly-
103 ash will improve compressive strength and reduces shrinkage. For this reason, 10% of
104 metakaolin was replaced by fly ash. To make the metakaolin, kaolin clay sourced from
105 the Southwest of England, UK was calcined at 800°C for a duration of 2 h in an electric
106 furnace. A solid:liquid ratio of 0.75 was chosen as this provided adequate workability for
107 pouring but is high enough to minimize impact on compressive strength (0.8 is optimal
108 [25]). A Na_2SiO_3 :NaOH ratio of 2 was used as this should provide the best compressive
109 strength, plus the 10M concentration of Na_2SiO_3 provides sufficient conductivity [21,26].
110 For additives, sand at 50% of solid mass was added as this is known to improve both
111 compressive strength and adhesion [27], with 50% being the optimal quantity [28]. Finally,
112 polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) fibres at 0.5% of solid mass will both reduce shrinkage and
113 improve adhesion to the substrate [29].

114 Every ingredient, their mass contribution and an example mass for the mix design
115 used in this work is given in Table 1. For information on the composition of the alumi-
116 nates used, refer to our previous work: metakaolin [16], fly-ash [30].

117 Small 30 mm × 30 mm × 25 mm prism samples of this mix design were crushed
118 in a compression machine. These experiments will provide a general indication of the
119 compressive strength of the material. BS EN 12190:1999 requires 40 mm cubes to be
120 tested, but this could not be done with the equipment available. Should this material be
121 used in a real world application, a more extensive mechanical analysis should be performed.
122 From a total of 13 prisms, an average compressive strength of 26 MPa was gained, with
123 a standard deviation of 6 MPa. This meets BS EN 1504:1999 for non-structural repair of
124 concrete (≥ 15 MPa).

125 2.1.3. Application to concrete

126 Prior to the AAM being applied, the concrete surface was wire brushed to improve
127 adhesion. The AAM repairs were then applied manually within a temporary mould
128 attached to the concrete surface. Stainless steel electrodes (plates or bolts) were inserted
129 to allow for later electrical coupling to the impedance analyser/ConcrEITS instrument.
130 Samples were then cured at room temperature in sealed containers for 28 days. This
131 produced concrete prism and cube samples (Fig. 1b and 1c) with adhered self-sensing
132 repair patches. For testing, samples are wrapped in plastic film to maintain constant
133 moisture level within the AAM.

134 2.2. ConcrEITS: Design and benchmarks

135 2.2.1. 4-probe impedance measurement: theory

136 Low-cost electrical impedance measuring devices for concrete have gained some
137 interest in recent years: Corva et al. [32] developed a miniaturised resistance measuring

Figure 1. a) Pure geopolymer sample used for benchmarking, b) 40 x 40 x 200 mm beam and c) 100 x 100 x 100 mm cube with instrumented AAM repair.

Table 1: Mix design for the self-sensing AAM repair material.

Material	Wt%	Example (g)
Metakaolin	32.02	273
Fly ash	3.17	27
Sand ($\leq 800 \mu\text{m}$)	17.58	150
PVA fibres (3 mm Length) [31]	0.35	3
Na_2SiO_3 solution	31.18	266
NaOH solution (10 M)	15.70	134

138 device for chloride ingress measurement in concrete; and Kaur et al. [33] developed a
 139 low cost electro-mechanical impedance device for damage detection in concrete using
 140 piezo-electric materials.

141 The electrical impedance of a specimen can be monitored via 2, 3, or 4-probe AC
 142 excitation (or DC excitation if electrical resistance is the quantity of interest). For
 143 an extensive overview of these methods, along with examples of when they should be
 144 deployed, see [34]. In this work, focus will be on 4-probe AC excitation using the Van
 145 der Pauw (VDP) method [35], as illustrated in Fig. 2 a).

146 In its ideal case, the VDP method consists of small “point” electrodes placed exactly
 147 in the corners of a thin, cloverleaf shaped cell. However, these ideal conditions are rarely
 148 even approximately met in real applications: electrodes have a finite area, cannot be placed
 149 exactly in the corners, and AAM patches need to have a suitable shape and thickness to
 150 be able to function as a repair. Weiss [36] states that the resistivity of a cell can still be
 151 accurately measured without meeting these conditions, for a square/rectangular cell and
 152 electrode array.

153 Equation (1) can be used to assess the 4-probe impedance measurement illustrated
 154 in Fig. 2 a). An applied current $I_a(\omega, t)$ results in a measured voltage $V_m(\omega, t)$ over the
 155 two opposite electrodes. This results in a bulk average measured impedance for the entire
 156 patch.

157 For AAMs, the electrical impedance consists of a resistive (Z_R) and a capacitive
 158 (Z_C) element [14], and there is, therefore; a phase difference, $\phi = \omega\Delta t$, between current
 159 and voltage, and a magnitude difference given by the impedance modulus, $|Z| = \frac{|V_m|}{|I_a|}$.

160 2.2.2. ConcrEITS instrument design

161 Version 1 of our circuit design was intended to interrogate discrete patch repairs
 162 via 4-probe electrical impedance spectroscopy (EIS). In EIS, impedance measurements
 163 are carried out over a range of excitation frequencies, ω . Interrogating concrete or a self-
 164 sensing repair’s response at various frequencies allows measured variables (e.g. moisture,
 165 sodium chloride contamination) to be elucidated and characterised if each measurand has
 166 a frequency-dependent response. To perform 4-probe EIS, a variable frequency voltage,
 167 V_a , is applied at the excitation electrodes and the resulting applied current is measured,
 168 I_a . At the two opposing electrodes, a summed voltage is also measured V_m . This is
 169 illustrated in Fig. 3.

170 To carry out these tasks, and keep costs low, an ATXMEGA128A4U [37] micro-
 171 controller unit (MCU) was chosen. The on-board 12 bit digital-to-analogue converter
 172 (DAC) is used with a lookup table which is accessed after varying time periods to produce
 173 the required multi-frequency applied voltage sinusoid, $V_a(\omega, t)$. The applied current, I_a ,
 174 is found by running V_a over a variable measurement resistor, R_m , before being amplified
 175 (A_1) using a TLC2262 chip and measured by an on-board 12-bit analogue-to-digital
 176 converter (ADC), V_{ADC1} . I_a is calculated in post-processing as:

$$I_a = \frac{V_{ADC1}}{R_m} \quad (2)$$

177 The measured voltage, V_m , is found via a summing amplifier (A_2) and then measured
 178 via a second ADC, V_{ADC2} . It can therefore be calculated, also in post-processing, via
 179 $V_m = \frac{V_{ADC2}}{A_2}$.

180 The minimum conversion times of $\approx 7 \mu s$ and $\approx 3.5 \mu s$ for the DAC and ADC
 181 respectively mean that our maximum excitation frequency is $f_a = \frac{\omega}{2\pi} = 4.7 \text{ kHz}$ for a 20
 182 sample sinusoid.

183 Data logging is done via a serial interface UART-to-USB device, or using a UART-
 184 to-bluetooth module when wireless communication is required. The device is compatible
 185 with battery operation, as it is low power, drawing ($\approx 95 \text{ mW}$), and uses a 3.4 V DC
 186 supply.

Figure 2. Configuration of electrodes in test samples: a) VDP method for measuring impedance, Z of a single 4-probe cell, b) serial tomographic measurement of 16-probe cell, V_a is applied over a single electrode pair (1 shown), whilst V_m is measured over all other 15 pairs (9 shown). This is repeated for every combination to give impedance array, $Z[x,y]$ where x is applying pair and y is measuring pair.

Figure 3. Simplified block diagram of ConcrEITS: a DAC from the MCU is used to apply an AC voltage, V_a , of varying frequency, f_a , which results in the applied current, I_a , over the excitation electrodes 1 & 2. A voltage is measured over opposing electrodes 3 & 4, V_m , to give the impedance of the AAM, Z . Voltage measurements are taken using the MCUs ADCs following suitable amplification by a TLC2262.

187 The total combined cost of components and manufacturing of a single ConcrEITS
 188 PCB is \$50 USD at low fabrication volumes.

189 2.2.3. ConcrEITS: Benchmarking

190 ConcrEITS was benchmarked against a commercial interrogator (which costs \$16k
 191 USD). Benchmarking was conducted on pure AAM block samples, as shown in Figure
 192 1 a). These samples are small (30 x 30 x 25 mm) to keep the impedance relatively low
 193 and distance between electrodes short. This will allow accurate measurements from both
 194 interrogators. Should larger samples be used then benchmarking should be repeated for
 195 larger samples to ensure measurement accuracy remains the same. The impedance of these
 196 samples should be similar to those used for crack detection experiments. Benchmarking
 197 ConcrEITS using a single 4-probe impedance measurement instead of tomographic
 198 impedance measurements should be sufficient as tomography is simply the act of taking
 199 these 4-probe measurements over various electrode configurations. Furthermore, no all-
 200 in-one tomography impedance interrogator is widely available commercially at the time
 201 of writing. A separate multiplexer would be required in order to carry out tomography
 202 using the commercial interrogator, adding to the cost. Both devices were programmed to
 203 perform EIS sweeps from f_a 100 Hz – 1200 Hz. This range should be sufficient enough to
 204 vary the samples impedance and is within ConcrEITS capabilities.

205 Results are shown in Fig. 4, where all impedance magnitude values have been
 206 normalized as:

$$Z_{norm} = \frac{|Z(f_a)|}{|Z(100\text{ Hz})|} \quad (3)$$

207 Fig. 4 a) shows an example response obtained by both interrogators for a single
 208 sample. It is clear that the commercial interrogator is more accurate and precise than

Figure 4. Results from interrogator comparison, a) normalised impedance magnitudes from a single sample EIS, and; b) the impedance magnitudes measured at all frequencies for seven individual samples.

209 the low-cost ConcrEITS. However, ConcrEITS is able to follow the trend of impedance
 210 changes fairly well and would provide an acceptable estimate of a sample's impedance.

211 For a closer comparison, Fig. 4 b) shows the impedance responses measured over
 212 seven individual AAM samples. The root mean square error (RMSE) between low-
 213 cost (ConcrEITS) and the commercial interrogator is $\pm 5.4\%$, which is adequate for our
 214 application.

215 2.3. ConcrEITS: Implementing tomography

216 With the successful demonstration of ConcrEITS for 4-probe EIS, the next stage was
 217 to look to the requirements for distributed impedance mapping via electrical impedance
 218 tomography (EIT).

219 2.3.1. Electrical impedance tomography: theory

220 EIT can be considered as the implementation of the impedance measurement outlined
 221 in Section 2.2.1, but over a larger number of electrodes placed around the perimeter of
 222 the sample. This is usually done via multiplexing, and is illustrated in Fig. 2 b) for
 223 16 electrodes. Every combination of electrodes is serially measured to provide a matrix
 224 of impedance values $Z(x, y)$, where x is the applying pair of electrodes, and y is the
 225 measuring pair. EITS is an extension of EIT, in which the frequencies are also altered
 226 during the measurement.

227 Historically, when discussing EIT, the electrical conductivity distribution, σ is
 228 described. This quantity is inversely proportional to the magnitude of the electrical
 229 impedance, $|Z|$, described above.

230 The objective of *difference imaging* in EIT is to produce a reconstructed colour
 231 contour image to analyse the change in conductivity (or impedance) distributions over
 232 time, relative to some baseline measurement. In contrast to absolute imaging, difference
 233 imaging is not sensitive to errors, such as electrode misplacements, misshapen bodies,
 234 and inhomogeneous materials. All of which are common in practical civil engineering
 235 applications. These benefits compensate somewhat for the reduced level of accuracy and
 236 spatial resolution compared to absolute imaging.

237 An in depth discussion of impedance mapping is provided in [38]. Briefly, EIT can
 238 be split into two main parts: 1) the forward problem, and; 2) the inverse problem. These
 239 are summarised below.

240 Forward problem

241 The forward problem is the prediction of the boundary voltages of a body based on
 242 its modelled conductivity distribution. It can be stated in simplified terms as:

$$V = F(\sigma) + n \quad (4)$$

243 where V is a vector of observed electrode potentials, $F(\cdot)$ is a function which maps
 244 conductivity, σ to those electrode potentials, V , and n is some measurement noise.

245 At a deeper level, the equation which is being solved is the non-linear Laplace
 246 equation:

$$\nabla \cdot (\sigma \nabla \mu) = 0 \text{ (within the body, } \Omega) \quad (5)$$

247 where $\sigma = \sigma(a)$ is the conductivity distribution over the body, and $\mu = \mu(a)$ is the
 248 voltage potential at any location, a in the body, Ω .

249 To gain unique solutions to Equation 5, boundary conditions are set: that is
 250 information about the electrodes which are being used to interrogate the body. The
 251 model chosen for the boundary conditions is the complete electrode model (CEM), which
 252 describes among other parameters, electrode contact impedances, and the voltages and
 253 currents between multiple electrodes.

254 The forward problem is then to solve the CEM with equation (5) over the area of
 255 the body. In practice, this is often achieved via discretization of the body using the finite
 256 element method. The body is usually meshed into triangular elements. This converts
 257 the mathematically complex forward problem into a series of equations to be solved by a
 258 computer.

259 The maturity of EIT in the medical field means that there are already available
 260 methods to solve the forward problem using open-source software. One example is
 261 the Electrical Impedance Tomography and Diffuse Optical Tomography Reconstruction
 262 Software (or EIDORS), which is used in this work.

263 Inverse problem

264 The purpose of the inverse problem is to utilize the forward model to estimate the
 265 conductivity change, $\delta\sigma$, following an event: in this paper, that could be a change in
 266 temperature of the AAM repair, or a crack. If we define an initial baseline conductivity
 267 measurement as $\sigma(t = t_0)$, and a second conductivity measurement after time t_1 as
 268 $\sigma(t = t_1)$, then the change is:

$$\delta\sigma = \sigma(t_1) - \sigma(t_0) \quad (6)$$

269 In the difference imaging method, a linearisation model is used to approximate the
 270 difference using equation (4) as:

$$\delta V = J\delta\sigma + \delta n \quad (7)$$

271 where $\delta V = V(t_1) - V(t_0)$ is the difference in voltage measurements, δn is any change
 272 in measurement noise and J is the Jacobian matrix of mapped conductivities to voltages
 273 from the forward model. From this, the objective is now to find $\delta\sigma$, which is done via
 274 minimization:

$$\delta\sigma_{min} = \arg \min_{\delta\sigma} [||J\delta\sigma - \delta V||_2^2 + p_\sigma(\sigma)] \quad (8)$$

275 where $\delta\sigma_{min}$ is the minimized change in conductivity and $p_\sigma(\sigma)$ is a regularization term.

276 The inverse problem is ill-posed, because it has non-unique solutions. In other
 277 words, multiple conductivity distributions could lead to identical boundary voltages.
 278 The regularisation term $p_\sigma(\sigma)$ is therefore required to obtain stable solutions. Tikhonov
 279 regularization is the most common method, and incorporates the assumption that the
 280 conductivity distribution is smooth [39]. Tikhonov regularisation was used for simplicity
 281 and using other methods could improve results in future.

282 2.3.2. ConcrEITS: multiplexing hardware implementation

283 The only additional hardware requirement to realise tomographic imaging is to
 284 perform impedance measurements over multiple pins via multiplexing. Due to the small

size of the samples in this work, 16 pins were assumed to provide enough spatial resolution without over-complicating the circuit. For larger AAM repairs samples, more electrodes may be required. From Fig. 3, each of the four connections (labelled 1-4) are interconnected to separate 16-by-1 multiplexers. Each multiplexer is controlled via 4 digital outputs from the micro-controller. This means each connection from the interrogator to the AAM repair can be switched to any of the 16 electrodes at any time. The full final circuit diagram is shown in Fig. 5 and the PCB is shown in Fig. 6.

In the results presented in this paper, the firmware was updated to serially measure every combination of electrodes as previously illustrated in Fig. 2 b) using a single frequency AC excitation of 1 kHz. A swept excitation can also be implemented. The electrode potentials, $|V_m|$ and injected currents, $|I_a|$, are extracted and fed into the EIDORS software, along with patch and electrode parameters. The total cost of ConcrEITS including multiplexing is around \$60 USD at low production volumes.

3. Results

The output of EIDORS consists of a reconstructed contour image of the conductivity change between two states separated by time. For convenience, contour images are normalised and set to the same magnitude limits, allowing direct comparison between samples. Results are described in reference to change in conductivity, $\delta\sigma$. Given $|Z| \propto \sigma^{-1}$, a lower conductivity corresponds to a higher impedance. Low conductivities are represented as “black” in the contour and high conductivities as “white”.

3.0.1. Thermal variations

Initial testing of ConcrEITS for EIT involved detection and location of temperature changes over a $100\text{ mm} \times 100\text{ mm}$ patch. This test was chosen as it is non-destructive and could be repeated indefinitely. Our previous work [15], has shown that increases in AAM temperature cause increases in conductivity.

Results from a representative test are shown in Table 2. Heat is applied to the surface of the patch using heated ceramic dishes. In test T1, the dish is placed in the top right of the patch. The heat is removed after a period of time and the patch is allowed to cool before placing heat in a different location for subsequent tests T2 and T3.

The tomographic reconstruction shows that the resulting thermal variations are detectable from the electrical measurements. However, it is clear that discretely located temperature changes are dispersed, due to the low thermal conductivity of the AAM and the high thermal inertia of the concrete substrate. This may be why the system is unable to distinguish between two heated dishes during test T3.

Although interesting, these results show that despite being reversible, temperature mapping has its limitations as a testing and validation procedure for this system. In future, if temperature becomes the intended measure, a thermocouple will be embedded within the AAM during testing to better understand heat dispersion in the AAM.

3.0.2. Crack detection and location

To test damage detection and location using ConcrEITS, small-scale concrete beam bending experiments were carried out, as shown in Fig. 7. Loading machine contacts were insulated from the sample. AAM was applied to six $40\text{ mm} \times 40\text{ mm} \times 200\text{ mm}$ singly reinforced concrete beams, producing samples denoted SB1, SB2, ..., SB6. Beams underwent linear 4-point bending (displacement rate = -0.01 mm/s) until cracks were visually distinguishable. Tomographic measurements of the system were taken continuously throughout.

Fig. 8 shows sample SB5 image reconstruction over time. The system is clearly able to detect and locate cracks as they appear and begin to widen as load is increased over time. As expected, cracking leads to a localized decrease in conductivity (or increase in impedance), as it disrupts the pathways for ions migration in the AAM and concrete.

Figure 5. Multiplexer wiring diagram for ConcrEITS. Four multiplexers are used to switch the 4-probe signals over any combination of the 16 electrodes, as in Fig. 2 b). Each multiplexer is switched using 4 digital outputs from the MCU.

Figure 6. PCB of final ConcrEITS circuit with addressing wires. A UART to USB or UART to BLE module is used for data transmission.

Table 2: Thermal variance detection and localisation results from tomographic reconstruction.

	Ref. Heat location im- age	Tomographic recon- struction
T1		
T2		
T3		

Figure 7. Small-scale beam bending experimental set-up, with 16 electrodes interrogating an AAM patch on the concrete surface. Green tape was used to insulate the loading machine from the sample.

Figure 8. Sample SB5 tomographic reconstruction over time: each rectangle in the grid represents a single tomographic impedance difference image against the initial state. Each image frame represents the passing of 3 minutes in time.

Table 3: Beam sample crack detection and localisation results from tomographic reconstruction.

Sample	Crack image	Tomographic reconstruction
SB1		
SB2		
SB3		
SB4		
SB5		
SB6		

335 Table 3 shows a final photograph of the AAM surface of each sample (SB1 to SB6)
336 after testing is complete, and compares it with the final tomographic image reconstruction.
337 Electrodes 1 through 16 are numbered. In every case tested, cracks are detected and
338 located successfully at *their initiation and exit points*, i.e. where the cracks propagate
339 between electrodes.

340 For example, sample SB1 cracked between electrodes 11 and 12 which then prop-
341 agated upwards to between electrodes 4 and 5. This is correctly measured from the
342 tomographic reconstruction image. In cases where multiple cracks occur, such as SB5
343 which cracks between electrodes 10 and 11, 14 and 15 then 3 and 4: these are all observed
344 in the tomographic reconstruction, with black contours appearing in these locations
345 representing a decrease in conductivity. However, it is clear that accurate quantification
346 of crack shapes and widths cannot be ascertained from these reconstructions.

347 We believe there are two main reasons for this. Firstly, difference imaging is
348 inherently less accurate than absolute imaging [8], therefore; we would need to minimize
349 the associated errors (electrode misplacements, misshapen body, inhomogeneity) and
350 model the electrode contact impedance to gain more accurate representations of the
351 cracks through absolute imaging. Secondly, accuracy of the overall system itself, including
352 interrogator voltage measurements and number of electrodes, will affect the resolution of
353 the image reconstruction.

354 Nevertheless, ConcrEITS has demonstrated that is able to generally detect and
355 locate cracks, and provide some measure of severity. Furthermore the system provided
356 no spurious results - there were no false positives or negatives. That is, no cracks were
357 undetected and there were no large decreases in conductivity at locations without cracks.
358 Overall, these results show that the low-cost, low-power ConcrEITS shows promise as a
359 crack detection system for AAM repairs and potentially other self-sensing coatings which
360 encode measurands as a conductivity change.

361 4. Discussion

362 Results in this paper represent a validation of ConcrEITS as a low-cost distributed
363 crack detection system using AAM self-sensing repairs. This section will firstly analyse
364 the results before discussing various parts of the research and how they could be improved
365 for the future.

366 4.1. Analysing results

367 Initial testing attempted to measure distributed temperature changes in a 100 mm
368 \times 100 mm patch. This sought a simple, fast and repeatable experiment to validate the
369 interrogator measurements. However, it is clear from the thermal variation images (Table
370 2 that distributed temperature changes are not detectable using ConcrEITS. A general
371 change in temperature can be measured, but location is indistinguishable.

372 To validate crack detection, various small scale concrete samples (40 mm \times 40 mm
373 \times 200 mm) beams with manually deployed AAM patches over a single surface were
374 tested. Results show that distributed crack measurements over time are possible with
375 ConcrEITS, although locations are general and exact crack widths, shapes and lengths
376 are indistinguishable. Nevertheless, these results show promise for the use of ConcrEITS
377 and AAM on large area concrete as a distributed crack detection system.

378 4.2. Future work

379 4.2.1. Improve consistency of AAM deployment

380 From Fig. 1 b) and c) it is clear the deployment of AAM is inconsistent: electrodes
381 are misaligned and edges are uneven. In future this will be improved by using custom
382 made moulds and templates. Additionally, ongoing research into automated deployment
383 may solve these issues [16].

384 4.2.2. Up-scaled experiments

385 Research in this paper demonstrates the capability of ConcrEITS to detect and
386 locate cracks in small scale samples. Identifying the location of a crack in such a small
387 area has little to no use in an industrial context. The final objective of ConcrEITS is to
388 perform distributed crack detection over a large area covered with an AAM. Future work
389 will look to upscale the research in this paper to larger areas, working towards a site
390 deployment. This will also require benchmarking against the commercial interrogator for
391 larger samples.

392 4.2.3. Increase frequency of AC excitation

393 In Section 2.2 ConcrEITS was compared to a commercial interrogator in 4-probe
394 EIS over a small frequency range (100 - 1200 Hz). The max applied frequency of the
395 commercial interrogator is 1 MHz, compared to ConcrEITS' 4.7 kHz for a 20 sample
396 sinusoid. The major limitation on this is the conversion time of the DAC (7 μ s) and
397 ADC (3.5 μ s). For EIS measurements, the ability to apply much higher frequency signal
398 may be required. It is proposed that in future work, a separate excitation circuit will be
399 constructed to apply the AC voltage, removing the delay caused by the DAC. Using just
400 the ADC for sampling, and taking less samples per sinusoidal period should allow use of
401 an AC frequency of up to 100 kHz.

402 4.2.4. Improve measurement accuracy

403 In terms of resolution, the MCU uses 12-bit ADC and 12-bit DAC, which for a V_{CC}
404 of 3.3V gives ± 0.8 mV. For an excitation voltage magnitude of 0.1 V this is sufficient.
405 However, the benchmark against a commercial interrogator resulted in a ± 5.4 % RMSE.
406 In future, this error will be minimized. Implementation of filters such as high-pass filters
407 and unity gain amplifiers may remove any background noise and improve the accuracy.

408 5. Conclusions

409 In this paper, we have presented ConcrEITS: a low-cost (\$60 USD) interrogator for
410 tomographic and spectroscopic impedance mapping of concretes coated with conductive
411 coatings. The system was demonstrated for an alkali-activated-material based repair.
412 ConcrEITS was able to measure impedance to ± 5.4 % RMSE when benchmarked against
413 a commercial impedance analyser. It was able to map concrete temperature variations
414 with some degree of success, although temperature measurements were blurred due to
415 the high thermal inertia of the concrete substrate. The system was also able to detect
416 and broadly locate cracking in small-scale concrete beams with no spurious results.
417 Future work will look to further test the system with scaled up 1 m long concrete beams
418 instrumented with larger patches.

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433 Abbreviations

434 The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

435

EITS	Electrical impedance tomography and spectroscopy
AAM	Alkali-activated material
ERT	Electrical resistance tomography
EIS	Electrical impedance spectroscopy
EIT	Electrical impedance tomography
USD	United states dollar
VDP	Van der Pauw
MCU	Micro-controller Unit
436 ADC	Analogue-to-digital converter
DAC	Digital-to-analogue converter
UART	Universal asynchronous receiver-transmitter
USB	Universal Serial Bus
RMSE	Root mean square error
CEM	Complete electrode model
EIDORS	Electrical impedance tomography and diffuse optical tomography reconstruction
PCB	Printed circuit board

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